

Single atom engineering for catalysis and energy storage

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Functional low-dimensional materials with judicious molecular and single-atom engineering may unlock versatile platforms for high-performance electrochemical energy storage and efficient, earth-abundant catalysis. In the first part of the talk I will discuss about how tailored graphene derivatives and organic architectures can push the limits of batteries and supercapacitors with the aid of single metal ions. The second part highlights catalytic applications that exploit materials of such design, which are key to decreasing the energy and environmental footprint of the chemicals industry. An aminoacid-anchored graphene acid organocatalyst outperforms homogeneous acids for solvent-free valorization of waste organics and for biofuel production. Embedding earth abundant transition metal atoms in such graphene derivatives affords redox-switchable mixed-valence catalysts that efficiently drive aerobic oxidative transformations of lower-value molecules to key chemicals for the pharmaceutical and polymer industry. These studies demonstrate how molecularly functionalized materials and metal-carbon seamless architectures can deliver advances in catalysis for low energy organic transformations and electrochemical energy storage technologies.

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